

Synthesis and Characterisation of some Second Transition Elements Complexes with Pyrrolealdazine

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The azines derived from 2-heterocyclicaldehydes can coordinate to metal ions in different manners. Complexes with some ions of first series of transition elements have aroused considerable interest¹⁻³. Recently, an increasing number of metal complexes with salicylaldazine and substituted benzaldazine have been studied^{4,5}.

In the present work, new metal-azine complexes of the second transition elements have been synthesised and characterised.

Results and Discussion

Analytical data (Table 1) reveal that the complexes possess 1 : 2 and 2 : 2 metal-to-ligand ratio. The complexes are found insoluble in water, moderately soluble in methanol and soluble in ethanol, DMF and DMSO. Their molar con-

ductivity values (Table 1) indicate 1 : 2, 1 : 4 and 1 : 5 electrolytes⁶.

The assignments of the infrared spectral bands of the ligand and their complexes are based on the literature^{7,8}. Tridentate and tetradentate nature of the azine ligand have been achieved by coordination through the nitrogen of the azine group and the nitrogen from two heterocyclic rings.

The infrared spectra for PA showed a sharp band of medium intensity at 1640–1625 cm⁻¹ which may be assigned to the azomethine C=N stretching vibration^{1,8}. This band splitted into two peaks at 1640 and 1580 cm⁻¹ in the spectra of the Nb^V and Zr^{IV} complexes, which indicates coordination of only one azine nitrogen to the metal ions^{3,4}. Whereas in the Pd^{II}, Ag^I and Cd^{II} complexes this band shifted to lower frequency

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Sl no	Compd	Colour	M p °C	Analysis% Found/(Calcd)					Mol cond Ω ⁻¹ cm ² mol ⁻¹	
				C	H	N	M*	C ⁻	DMF	EtOH
1	[Zr(PA) ₂](NO ₃) ₄	Yellowish orange	178d	33.97 (33.74)	3.15 (2.81)	23.81 (23.62)	12.92 (12.83)	—	300	160
2	[Nb(PA) ₂]Cl ₅	Yellow	226	37.66 (37.36)	3.43 (3.11)	18.08 (17.43)	14.53 (14.46)	27.85 (27.63)	360	200
3	[Pd ₂ (PA) ₂](NO ₃) ₄	Dark green	240	28.02 (28.82)	2.88 (2.40)	20.99 (20.17)	25.93 (25.55)	—	300	160
4	[Ag ₂ (PA) ₂](NO ₃) ₂	Green	136d	33.36 (33.72)	2.26 (2.81)	18.92 (19.67)	30.45 (30.31)	—	140	80
5	[Cd ₂ (PA) ₂](NO ₃) ₄	Green	166	29.22 (28.41)	2.51 (2.37)	19.86 (19.89)	26.90 (26.61)	—	300	160

*M = Zr^{IV}, Nb^V, Pd^{II}, Ag^I and Cd^{II}

(1580 cm^{-1}) and the peak at 1640 cm^{-1} disappeared, which indicates coordination of the two azine nitrogen to the metal ions². The infrared band for the ligand at 1530 cm^{-1} ($\text{C} \equiv \text{N} \equiv \text{C}$)^{1,3} underwent positive shift upon complexation (1600 cm^{-1}), suggesting the presence of a M-N bond (where M = metal ion).

Therefore, the azine ligand with four coordination sites can act as tridentate ligand in the Zr^{IV} and Nb^{V} complexes, by utilising both the $\text{C} \equiv \text{N} \equiv \text{C}$ (from two heterocyclic rings) groups and one of the azomethine groups as bonding sites³. While in the Pd^{II} , Ag^{I} and Cd^{II} complexes, the ligand can act as tetradentate by utilising both the $\text{C} \equiv \text{N} \equiv \text{C}$ groups and the two azomethine groups as bonding sites, forming a bridged binuclear complexes.

The positive shift in N-N vibration on complexation (from 960 to 980-990 cm^{-1}) further corroborates the coordination of nitrogen atom to the metal ion⁹. The infrared spectra of the Zr^{IV} , Pd^{II} , Ag^{I} and Cd^{II} complexes show a strong band at about 1380 cm^{-1} due to ionic NO_3^- group³. On the other hand, the spectra of the complexes show new bands around 520-540 cm^{-1} , which are likely to be due to $\nu_{\text{M-N}}$ ¹⁰. The presence of these bands strongly supports coordination of the ligand with the metal ions.

The elemental analysis, molar conductance values, and the spectral observations indicate that the complexes have the formula $[\text{Zr}(\text{PA})_2](\text{NO}_3)_4$, $[\text{Nb}(\text{PA})_2]\text{Cl}_5$, $[\text{Pd}_2(\text{PA})_2](\text{NO}_3)_4$, $[\text{Ag}_2(\text{PA})_2](\text{NO}_3)_2$ and $[\text{Cd}_2(\text{PA})_2](\text{NO}_3)_4$.

Experimental

2-Pyrrolealdazine (PA) was prepared by the condensation of hydrazine sulphate with 2-pyrrolealdehyde in 1 : 2 molar ratio in ammonium hydroxide according to the standard method¹¹ (yellow crystals, m.p. 184°).

For the preparation of the complexes, methanolic solutions of metal salts ($\text{Zr}(\text{NO}_3)_4 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, NbCl_5 ,

$\text{Pd}(\text{NO}_3)_2$, AgNO_3 and $\text{Cd}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$) were treated separately with a methanolic solution of PA in 1 : 2 or 2 : 2 metal-to-ligand ratio. The mixture was refluxed for 1 h, then evaporated to about half of its volume, cooled and the resulting solid was washed with cold methanol, recrystallised from methanol and dried.

C, H and N were estimated by using a Carlo-Erba-Strumentazione 1106 analyser. The metal and chloride contents were determined by standard methods¹². Conductivity was measured with a MC-1 instrument using 10^{-3} M DMF and absolute ethanol solutions at room temperature. The infrared spectra (KBr) were recorded on Perkin - Elmer 557 spectrophotometer.

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